

TEACHING ESSAY WRITING WITH THE ELECTIC METHOD: STRATEGIES FOR INTERMEDIATE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract: This study explores the eclectic method's impact on essay writing, showing significant improvements in coherence, grammar, and vocabulary, alongside increased student confidence and engagement. While effective, some students struggled to adapt, underscoring the need for structured support. The findings highlight its flexibility for enhancing writing skills in a supportive setting.

Keywords: eclectic method, writing proficiency, student engagement, university education, peer review, process-oriented writing.

Аннотация: Это исследование изучает влияние эклектического метода на развитие навыков написания эссе, демонстрируя значительные улучшения в связности, грамматике и лексике, а также повышение уверенности и вовлеченности студентов. Несмотря на эффективность, некоторые студенты испытывали трудности с адаптацией, что подчеркивает необходимость структурированной поддержки. Выводы подчеркивают гибкость этого метода для улучшения навыков письма в поддерживающей среде.

Ключевые слова: эклектический метод, навыки письма, вовлеченность студентов, высшее образование, рецензирование, процесс-ориентированное письмо.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot esse yozish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishda eklektik usulning ta‘sirini o‘rganadi va izchillik, grammatika hamda lug‘at boyligini oshirishda sezilarli yutuqlarni, shuningdek, talabalarining ishonchi va qiziqishi oshganini ko‘rsatadi. Samaradorligiga qaramay, ba‘zi talabalar moslashishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelgan, bu esa tuzilgan yordamning zarurligini ta‘kidlaydi. Xulosalar, ushbu usulning yozish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishda moslashuvchanligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: eklektik usul, yozuv ko'nikmasi, talabalar ishtiroki, universitet ta'limi, tengdoshlar bahosi, jarayon yo'naltirilgan yozuv.

INTRODUCTION

Essay writing is a key academic skill that helps students think critically, organize their ideas, and communicate effectively. Intermediate-level university students often struggle with organizing arguments, ensuring grammatical accuracy, and following academic conventions.¹⁴ Traditional methods, such as grammar-translation and product-based approaches, often isolate language components, leading to a fragmented understanding of writing.¹⁵ The eclectic method offers a flexible approach, integrating elements of process-oriented, genre-based, and task-based methodologies, thus addressing a variety of student needs.¹⁶ This paper investigates how the eclectic method fosters both linguistic proficiency and academic writing competence among intermediate students.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The teaching of essay writing has undergone significant evolution, influenced by various educational methods. Traditional approaches, such as grammar-translation, emphasized grammatical accuracy but often overlooked the development of effective writing skills.¹⁷ Conversely, the direct method, while focusing on oral communication, treated writing as secondary, limiting students' ability to produce coherent essays.

A pivotal shift occurred with Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which positioned writing as an essential communicative skill. CLT stressed both grammatical correctness and the ability to express and organize ideas effectively. Furthermore, the process-oriented approach, which encourages students to engage in brainstorming, drafting, revising, and editing, has been shown to improve writing fluency and

¹⁴ Lee, S., Kim, J., & Park, T. (2021). Academic Writing Skills Development. *Educational Research Press*, pp. 45-47.

¹⁵ Johnson, R., & Tran, L. (2022). Revisiting Traditional Language Teaching Methods: Implications for Writing Instruction. *Language Studies Journal*, 8(2), pp. 89-91.

¹⁶ Murray, S. (2023). Integrative Approaches in Language Teaching: A Focus on the Eclectic Method. *Educational Review of Language Instruction*, 15(3), pp. 87-91.

¹⁷ Johnson, R., & Tran, L. (2022). Revisiting Traditional Language Teaching Methods: Implications for Writing Instruction. *Language Studies Journal*, 8(2), pp. 89-91.

creativity.¹⁸ This method fosters students’ confidence by allowing them to articulate ideas before focusing on accuracy.

Genre-based approaches, supported by Widdowson, have also proven valuable.¹⁹ These approaches enable students to recognize and apply writing conventions tailored to different contexts, thereby improving the structure and quality of their essays. In Uzbekistan, Khamraev²⁰ and Rahimova²¹ emphasize genre-based methods, which help students structure arguments and organize content effectively.

The eclectic method integrates multiple teaching strategies—process-oriented, genre-based, and task-based approaches—making it highly adaptable for diverse student needs.²² Research by Ellabib further underscores the positive impact of the eclectic method on writing skills, despite some challenges in its implementation.²³ This flexibility allows for customized lessons that support both language development and understanding of academic writing conventions.

Our recent research on task-based language teaching (TBLT) also highlights its efficacy in enhancing writing skills by promoting authentic communication.²⁴ By engaging students in real-world tasks, TBLT encourages meaningful participation, which can be incorporated within an eclectic framework to further enrich the writing process.

A mixed-methods approach was employed to evaluate the effectiveness of the eclectic method in an essay writing course. Quantitative data were collected through pre- and post-instruction writing assessments that measured improvements in coherence, organization, argumentation, grammar, and vocabulary. Qualitative data

¹⁸ Huang, Y., & Gao, L. (2023). Process-Oriented Approaches in Writing Instruction. *Journal of Modern Language Education*, 12(4), pp. 102-105.

¹⁹ Widdowson, H. G. (2022). *Functional Approaches to Language Learning and Teaching*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 134-137.

²⁰ Khamraev, A. (2023). Adapting Genre-Based Writing Instruction for Uzbek Learners. *Journal of Central Asian Educational Studies*, 9(2), pp. 45-49.

²¹ Rahimova, N. (2023). Advancements in Genre-Based Methods for Writing Instruction. *Tashkent Educational Research Journal*, 6(1), pp. 22-26.

²² Murray, S. (2023). Integrative Approaches in Language Teaching: A Focus on the Eclectic Method. *Educational Review of Language Instruction*, 15(3), pp. 87-91.

²³ Ellabib, M. (2023). Teacher Perceptions of the Eclectic Method in Writing Skill Development. *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 12(4), pp. 98-102.

²⁴ Yuldasheva, M., & Ergashev, R. (2023). Analyzing Task-Based Writing Approaches: Global Perspectives and Practices. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 4(2), pp. 75-80.

were gathered through interviews and classroom observations to assess students' experiences and perceptions.

Thirty third-year linguistics students enrolled in a reading and writing course participated. Two groups were taught using the eclectic method, which combined process-oriented, genre-based, and task-based approaches. The instructional methods included drafting, revising, peer-editing, and collaborative brainstorming, supported by scaffolding techniques such as graphic organizers and ongoing feedback.

Data analysis involved paired t-tests for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative insights. This combined approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of how the eclectic method impacted students' writing skills and engagement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study revealed a substantial improvement in students' writing proficiency after applying the eclectic method. Average post-assessment scores rose from 62% to 82%, with specific gains in coherence (65% to 82%), argumentation (60% to 80%), grammar (63% to 84%), and vocabulary (62% to 83%). These results underscore the eclectic method's effectiveness in addressing diverse writing skills within an essay-writing course.

Student engagement also increased, with 80% of participants reporting greater confidence in their writing by the end of the course. Peer reviews and real-world writing topics contributed to this improvement, with 75% of students finding that writing on relevant topics boosted their motivation. These findings highlight how the eclectic method supports both skill development and a supportive learning environment.

Some challenges emerged, however, as 35% of students struggled to adapt to the method's flexible, process-oriented approach, preferring more structured formats. This suggests a need for clear guidance and structured support to help students transition smoothly.

Compared to traditional methods, the eclectic approach significantly improved student confidence and engagement. In past semesters, only 45% felt confident in their

writing, whereas 80% did so under the eclectic method. Engagement also rose, with participation in writing tasks increasing from 50% to 75%.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the eclectic method effectively enhances both writing proficiency and student engagement in university essay courses. Improvements in writing skills—including coherence, argumentation, grammar, and vocabulary—demonstrate its capacity to meet diverse student needs, while increased confidence and engagement indicate its role in creating a positive classroom environment.

Challenges during the transition to this method highlight the need for clear, structured support, especially for students used to more prescriptive methods. Incorporating real-world topics and peer reviews fosters engagement and relevance, making the eclectic method a valuable tool for teaching writing at the university level.

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